

Análise Fatorial Confirmatória do SMAT

A Análise Fatorial Confirmatória – (AFC), foi realizada no JASP
(<https://jasp-stats.org/download/>)

1 – Configurações da AFC no JASP Ver 0.16

Additional fit measures
 R-Squared
 Implied covariance matrix
 Residual covariance matrix
 Modification indices
Cutoff 3.84
 Show lavaan syntax

▼ Multigroup CFA
Grouping variable <no choice> Invariance testing Configurational ▼

▼ Plots
Plots
 Misfit plot
 Model plot
 Show parameters
 Standardized
 Show means

▼ Advanced
Emulation
 None
 Mplus
 EQS
Error calculation
CI width 95.0 %
Method
 Standard
 Robust
 Bootstrap CI
Bootstrap samples 1000
Estimator
 Auto
 ML
 GLS
 WLS
 ULS
 DWLS
Standardization
 None
 Latents
 All
 No X

2 – Resultados da AFC

Model fit ▼

Chi-square test

Model	χ^2	df	p
Baseline model	2412.037	300	
Factor model	160.226	269	1.000

χ^2 : No teste de Chi-square (χ^2), temos $p > 0.05$. Logo, o modelo testado se adequa à base de dados utilizada.

Additional fit measures ▼

Fit indices ▼

Index	Value
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	1.000
Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI)	1.057
Bentler-Bonett Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI)	1.057
Bentler-Bonett Normed Fit Index (NFI)	0.934
Parsimony Normed Fit Index (PNFI)	0.837
Bollen's Relative Fit Index (RFI)	0.926
Bollen's Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	1.051
Relative Noncentrality Index (RNI)	1.052

TLI: O índice de adequação do modelo (TLI) é um índice de ajuste incremental que compara o modelo especificado com um modelo nulo e um modelo saturado. O valor do TLI acima de 0,95 indicam um bom ajuste do modelo.

CFI: O índice de ajuste comparativo (CFI) é outro índice de ajuste incremental que compara o modelo especificado com um modelo nulo e um modelo saturado. O valor do CFI acima de 0,95 indicam um bom ajuste do modelo.

Other fit measures ▼

Metric	Value
Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.000
RMSEA 90% CI lower bound	0.000
RMSEA 90% CI upper bound	0.000
RMSEA p-value	1.000
Standardized root mean square residual (SRMR)	0.090
Hoelter's critical N ($\alpha = .05$)	172.225
Hoelter's critical N ($\alpha = .01$)	182.016
Goodness of fit index (GFI)	0.952
McDonald fit index (MFI)	1.842
Expected cross validation index (ECVI)	3.059

RMSEA: é um índice de ajuste absoluto que mede a discrepância média entre o modelo especificado e os dados observados. O valor do RMSEA varia de 0 a 1, e valores abaixo de 0,05 indicam um bom ajuste do modelo.

3 – Validação Convergente e Discriminante

Parameter estimates ▼

Factor loadings ▼

Factor	Indicator	Symbol	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval		Std. Est. (all)
							Lower	Upper	
IR	QN1	λ_{11}	0.706	0.136	5.205	< .001	0.440	0.972	0.632
	QN2	λ_{12}	0.297	0.120	2.469	0.014	0.061	0.534	0.339
	QN3	λ_{13}	1.096	0.137	8.027	< .001	0.829	1.364	0.816
	QN4	λ_{14}	0.401	0.160	2.500	0.012	0.087	0.716	0.382
	QN5	λ_{15}	1.212	0.117	10.391	< .001	0.984	1.441	0.877
SP	QI3	λ_{21}	0.585	0.107	5.488	< .001	0.376	0.794	0.629
	QI4	λ_{22}	0.322	0.112	2.884	0.004	0.103	0.541	0.399
	QI10	λ_{23}	0.931	0.108	8.610	< .001	0.719	1.143	0.707
	QI11	λ_{24}	0.844	0.118	7.181	< .001	0.614	1.075	0.748
	QI19	λ_{25}	0.823	0.149	5.520	< .001	0.531	1.115	0.734
DE	QI1	λ_{31}	0.921	0.118	7.800	< .001	0.689	1.152	0.685
	QI2	λ_{32}	0.826	0.117	7.070	< .001	0.597	1.055	0.792
	QI5	λ_{33}	0.564	0.100	5.657	< .001	0.369	0.760	0.566
	QI6	λ_{34}	0.674	0.176	3.826	< .001	0.329	1.019	0.593
	QI7	λ_{35}	1.079	0.106	10.144	< .001	0.870	1.287	0.798
	QI8	λ_{36}	0.633	0.136	4.660	< .001	0.367	0.899	0.579
	QI13	λ_{37}	0.421	0.106	3.977	< .001	0.214	0.629	0.466
	QI14	λ_{38}	0.787	0.138	5.717	< .001	0.517	1.057	0.666
CI	QI16	λ_{39}	1.061	0.119	8.896	< .001	0.827	1.295	0.822
	QI17	λ_{310}	1.011	0.110	9.176	< .001	0.795	1.227	0.727
	QI9	λ_{41}	0.635	0.179	3.540	< .001	0.283	0.986	0.514
	QI12	λ_{42}	0.611	0.123	4.965	< .001	0.370	0.852	0.691
	QI15	λ_{43}	0.637	0.102	6.266	< .001	0.438	0.836	0.710
	QI18	λ_{44}	0.750	0.124	6.045	< .001	0.507	0.994	0.798
	QI20	λ_{45}	0.655	0.133	4.920	< .001	0.394	0.916	0.641

Residual variances ▼

Indicator	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval		Std. Est. (all)
					Lower	Upper	
QN1	0.750	0.180	4.160	< .001	0.397	1.103	0.601
QN2	0.680	0.136	5.007	< .001	0.414	0.946	0.885
QN3	0.601	0.221	2.727	0.006	0.169	1.034	0.334
QN4	0.941	0.255	3.698	< .001	0.442	1.440	0.854
QN5	0.443	0.224	1.978	0.048	0.004	0.881	0.231
QI3	0.522	0.090	5.770	< .001	0.345	0.699	0.604
QI4	0.549	0.115	4.762	< .001	0.323	0.774	0.841
QI10	0.868	0.166	5.241	< .001	0.543	1.193	0.500
QI11	0.560	0.118	4.757	< .001	0.329	0.791	0.440
QI19	0.579	0.148	3.925	< .001	0.290	0.868	0.461
QI1	0.957	0.210	4.565	< .001	0.546	1.368	0.530
QI2	0.406	0.073	5.528	< .001	0.262	0.550	0.373
QI5	0.677	0.185	3.652	< .001	0.314	1.041	0.680
QI6	0.837	0.195	4.296	< .001	0.455	1.218	0.648
QI7	0.662	0.098	6.729	< .001	0.469	0.855	0.363
QI8	0.794	0.147	5.386	< .001	0.505	1.083	0.665
QI13	0.639	0.109	5.881	< .001	0.426	0.851	0.783
QI14	0.778	0.165	4.715	< .001	0.455	1.102	0.557
QI16	0.541	0.126	4.298	< .001	0.294	0.788	0.325
QI17	0.915	0.233	3.922	< .001	0.458	1.372	0.472
QI9	1.123	0.346	3.245	0.001	0.445	1.802	0.736
QI12	0.409	0.093	4.403	< .001	0.227	0.591	0.523
QI15	0.399	0.137	2.911	0.004	0.130	0.667	0.496
QI18	0.320	0.084	3.833	< .001	0.157	0.484	0.363
QI20	0.615	0.170	3.621	< .001	0.282	0.949	0.589

4 – Modelo Fatorial

